

in highly sensitive varieties. Weather records for February 1976 show a low minimum temperature of 9.7° C and an

average minimum temperature of 13.9° C. But no sudden fall in minimum temperature was recorded which possi-

bly explains why such severe cold injury symptoms had not been observed before. ■

Pest management and control DISEASES

Fungicide control of rice grain infection

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Grain infection caused by seed-borne fungal pathogens *Helminthosporium oryzae*, *Nigrospora oryzae*, *Acrocyli-drium oryzae*, and *Curvularia* sp. is a serious problem when crop ripening stage coincides with the monsoon. The effect of fungicides on the control of grain infection in IR20 was studied under wet field conditions.

Fungicides were sprayed twice, once at the milky stage and again a week

Effect of fungicides on grain infection and yield, Tirurkuppam, Tamil Nadu, India.

Fungicide	Application/ha ^a	Grain infection	Grain yield
Copper oxychloride 50% WP	1250 g	15.1	3.40
Edifenphos 50% EC	750 ml	14.6	3.39
Carbendazim 50% WP 500	g	16.7	3.35
Carboxin 75% WP	500 g	16.8	3.29
Mancozeb 75% WP	1250 g	17.1	3.28
Cuman-L 50% EC	1250 ml	17.0	3.27
Captafol 80% WP	750 g	17.0	3.13
Unsprayed control	—	17.3	3.18
C.D.		0.8	ns

^aEach application.

later. Control plots were sprayed with plain water. Infected grains in 5 ran-domly selected clumps were assessed at

harvest. Plots treated with edifenphos and copper oxychloride had the lowest grain infection (see table). ■

Rotten disease of azolla

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Paddy soils in northeast Thailand are more suitable for azolla propagation than soils in other regions. But azolla there has been damaged by an unknown disease.

Disease samples were collected at the RPB during September-November 1981. Two genera of fungi were isolated. One genus showed a whitish colony of small mycelium, the other a cream brown colony of larger mycelium. Both were grown on potato dextrose agar (PDA). The whitish small mycelium was found to be the causal agent of the symptoms of rotten disease on azolla. The fungus belongs to the genus *Myrothecium*. Its general morphology is:

— Hyaline septate mycelium, 2.5-3.8

1. Sporodochia of *Myrothecium* fungus causing rotten disease of azolla in Thailand.

× 10.3-30 μ, good growth on PDA. Conidiophores macronem-

atous, mononematous, closely packed together to form sporodo-